

Inherent Time
and Quantum-induced Reality;
a Sequential Universe Model

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ABSTRACT

The sheer amount of current research available, relating to a premise which was nearly abandoned in the von Neumann-Wigner interpretation, is testimony to the continued interest in quantum wave function collapse as a generator of our entire perceived reality. The idea of a progression of naturally-inherent *time* should take into consideration not only nature's obsession with efficiency, but also the unavoidable such as aging, memory, isotope decay, motion, and the human invention of imagined time increments. A base-line, inherent, elegant, numerical definition of time, along with its likely origin, is overdue, with minimal philosophical, consciousness-related, or holistic inferences.

INTRODUCTION

As is typical with most scientific endeavors, the approach here will be to reduce the system to comprehensible components, in this case, imagined layers or segments of the universe, Fig. 1.

Efficiency comes into play immediately. Assuming that quantum wave function collapse on a grand scale is the genesis of momentary reality as we know it, logic suggests that a completely new path in a now freshly created alternate multiverse, might not be the most efficient scenario. Archiving the refreshed present reality, with only the minimal changes dictated by probability, would allow for moment-to-moment change, yet retention of history; thus the same universe, but with an inherent *refresh rate*. (There may be no need to re-create the moon each time it is observed, when simply moving it slightly further along its trajectory, and perhaps adding a bit more dust to its surface, would suffice, see Fig. 2).

The progression of time can be viewed as one of nature's involuntary processes, although this author fully realizes that many readers view time as an exclusively human invention. As such, its characteristics will be addressed in this paper using intentionally over-simplified equations, including sample calculations for our universe globally. As a double-check on the viability of those calculations, their numerical results will be compared to current estimates of the rate of expansion of the known universe.

Before dismissing the above approach to the subject of inherent universe time, realize that were it not for

the success of the included sample calculations, this author might agree. More than a crude Newtonian treatment of a complex quantum scenario, the numerical results appear to be substantiative.

At this early stage of this paper, generally related background references are suggested [1,2,3,4,5,6], since the universe model assumed here, and its investigative strategy, are believed to be unique.

Figure 1. Visualization of the progression of time as theorized; an adaptation of the Minkowski space-time diagram [7]. The wave function collapse is shown as being non-instantaneous, and the result is envisioned as a segment (seg) of some volume; one of many such seamlessly consecutive segs comprising the universe. Each new subsequent seg then becomes a refreshed rendition of the prior seg.

The analogous double-slit experiment [8] is shown schematically aligned at right. © 2023 Kenneth Shotwell

Assumptions

- a). Finite universe(s) is assumed.
- b). WFC, Abbreviation for quantum Wave Function Collapse.
- c). seg, Abbreviation representing the space-time volume of the present time.
- d). c , Speed of light in a vacuum = 2.99×10^8 m/s.
- e). t_u , Age of our universe = 13.8×10^9 years [9], or 43.5×10^{16} s.
- f). V_u , Volume of our known universe = 4×10^{80} m³ [10].
- g). t_{seg} , duration of wave function collapse = $.1 \times 10^{-21}$ s. This value was chosen from the estimated range of $.1 \times 10^{-9} > t_{seg} > .1 \times 10^{-21}$ s [2]. This decision is based on the assumption that a smaller time duration would more faithfully encompass all that needed to be replicated or refreshed within the present *time*, including masses, energies, frequencies, distances, and time itself. Imagine re-playing a video at a different frame rate than its original recording. Either realism suffers or seamless viewing becomes impossible. A higher initial frame rate, so to speak, i.e., a correspondingly shorter time duration, suggests a better fidelity generally.
- h). Rate of expansion of the known universe = .007% per million years [11, 12].

The progression of time relative to its parent origin $t=0$ will be addressed theoretically, Fig. 1, then numerically by example, within limits of currently available ranges of variables, Fig. 2. The visualization of the present segment being at the top of the stacked universe (Fig. 2) is not to be taken literally.

Time can be thought of here as an *inherent natural refresh rate* born one segment at a time. Each present reality segment exhibits a seamless transition to the next segment, which then becomes part of history, each being the result of a segment-wide, and continuously streaming, Wave Function Collapse, WFT. Each segment emulates the entire previous universe segment but with slight changes, since the duration of each segment is very short. Also, each segment would be best re-named a *segue*, since its boundaries and

interfaces with adjacent segments should not be imagined as abrupt, but rather fluid, and again, seamless. The abbreviation *seg* will appear in the text and as a subscript to key values and variables.

Figure 2. Conceptual model of a finite universe of any size or shape which can be expressed as volume = area x height or $V_u = A h_u$. Since $A_u = A_{seg}$, then $V_{seg} = A h_{seg}$. Note that time t and height h are in different units (seconds and meters), therefore $t_{seg} \neq h_{seg}$ and $t_u \neq h_u$. © 2023 Kenneth Shotwell

Most of the values shown in Fig. 2 are available from the *Assumptions* previously listed. Other values will be produced for an example calculation. Only the value for h_{seg} remains elusive, and can be expressed as a ratio of $\frac{t_{seg}}{t_u}$, or specifically,

EQ. 1 height of the present seg, $h_{seg} = \left(\frac{t_{seg}}{t_u} \right) h_u$

For those unaccustomed to envisioning time in multiple dimensions, it will be helpful to reiterate that, similar to matter and energy, distance and time are similarly co-dependent, though in different scales of measurement. Square time (s^2) is routinely used in calculations of acceleration, and cubic time (s^3) is the basis of space-time itself. Henceforth, should the reader be questioning whether or not the discussion is referring to a volume of distance, or a volume of time, the answer is both.

Figure 3a. Traditional axes for incorporating time within distance. Though satisfactory for routine calculations, the underlying assumption is a perfect cube with (1 or 3) edges assigned a value of 1 second. The example with three d,t axes does imply a three-dimensional cubic second, however Fig. 3b at right is more geometrically correct.

Figure 3b. Obeying a key rule for adding dimensions, this tesseract conveys a better interpretation of time as a hyper space-time cubic second.

Fig. 3a and Fig. 3b will help demonstrate how our normally accepted idea of the phrase *per second* has been a disservice to mathematicians. *Per second* is a convenience since it assumes a perfect cube, each side equal to 1 second, such that 1^3 also equals 1. However when referring to *per second* in space-time, we are actually referring to *per cubic second*, i.e., a volume of time. Fig. 3b best expresses cubic time since it correctly displays time as it should be merged with three dimensional space. That is, it should be merged *perpendicular* to the former three distance dimension axes.

A problem arises when we assume that our per-cubic-second cube is perfect . The problem is, in our routine calculations, we have defined a cubic second as a perfect cube, when it is not, according to all accepted theories of relativity [13]. $1 \times 1 \times 1 \text{m}^3$ and $.5 \times .5 \times 4 \text{m}^3$ describe the same volume, however shape and direction are key in distorted space-time. As such, equations shown below which involve time will deserve specialized attention and subscripts.

Proceeding then toward time-based equations, the volume of each present seg V_{seg} , from the general equation $V=Ah$, would be:

EQ. 2 volume of space-time in the present, $V_{\text{seg}} = A h_{\text{seg}}$

and from the general equation for flow rate of a (incompressible) fluid, $Q=V/t$,

EQ. 3 flow rate of time in the present, $Q_{\text{seg}} = \frac{V_{\text{seg}}}{t_{\text{seg}}}$

A velocity of time progression v_t in the global universe can be expressed from the general equation for v in terms of Q and A , that is $v=Q/A$, and by the general definition of velocity, $v=d/t$,

EQ. 4 velocity of time in the present, assuming a 1x1x1 cubical second $v_t = \frac{Q_{\text{seg}}}{A} = \frac{h_{\text{seg}}}{t_{\text{seg}}}$ m/s

To be clear, this equation is meant to refer to a base-line *seg-inherent* (Fig. 3a) *velocity of time* itself, relative to its origin at $t=0$ (again, see Fig. 2). Along with the other parameters listed in the *Assumptions*, it is subject to local gravitational and time dilation effects. It is however a useful and comprehensible equation which will yield an actual numerical value, as will be shown in the *Sample Calculation*.

A return is necessary, at this point in the text, to traditional units of time (m/s), since values for our universe age and apparent expansion both assumed traditional 1x1x1 seconds.

Since most of the above equations are a function of volume, an opportunity would be missed here if the red-shift expansion of the universe were not mentioned. Such expansion may be due, in whole or in part, to an expansion of time. If a group of WFC-generated segs are added to the history of the universe during a million years, for example, then does the expansion rate of the universe coincide? In other words,

EQ. 5 $Q_{\text{seg}}/\text{million years} \stackrel{?}{\approx} .007\%$ of $V_u/\text{million years}$

where the rate of expansion of the universe is estimated at .007% every million years (see *Assumptions*).

Any *acceleration* of the expansion rate of the universe is beyond the scope of this paper, however with the expansion of the volume of the universe comes increase of area A_{seg} , and that area increase is related to acceleration in the model envisioned in this paper.

Sample Calculation

A numerical calculation can now be generated if some geometry for our universe is assumed. A volume for our universe $V_u = 4 \times 10^{80} \text{ m}^3$ (see *Assumptions*) can be the product of, say, an area $A = 4 \times 10^{60} \text{ m}^2$ and a height $h_u = 1 \times 10^{20} \text{ m}$. Other aspect ratios will yield equivalent results since area decreases as height increases, and vice-versa. Equations 1 through 5 can now be calculated using these numerical values:

$$V_u = 4 \times 10^{80} \text{ m}^3 \text{ (see } \textit{Assumptions})$$

$$A = 4 \times 10^{60} \text{ m}^2 \text{ (calculated above)}$$

$$h_u = 1 \times 10^{20} \text{ m (calculated above)}$$

$$t_{\text{seg}} = .1 \times 10^{-21} \text{ s (see } \textit{Assumptions})$$

$$t_u = 43.5 \times 10^{16} \text{ s (see } \textit{Assumptions})$$

$$\text{from EQ. 1} \quad h_{\text{seg}} \approx \left(\frac{.1 \times 10^{-21}}{43.5 \times 10^{16}} \right) 1 \times 10^{20} \approx .23 \times 10^{-19} \text{ m}$$

$$\text{from EQ. 2} \quad V_{\text{seg}} \approx 4 \times 10^{60} (.23 \times 10^{-19}) \approx .92 \times 10^{41} \text{ m}^3$$

$$\text{from EQ. 3} \quad Q_{\text{seg}} \approx \frac{.92 \times 10^{41}}{.1 \times 10^{-21} \text{ s}} \approx 9.2 \times 10^{62} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$$

$$\text{from EQ. 4} \quad v_t \approx \frac{9.2 \times 10^{62}}{4 \times 10^{60}} = \frac{.23 \times 10^{-19}}{.1 \times 10^{-21}} \approx 230 \text{ m/s}$$

$$\text{from EQ. 5} \quad Q_{\text{seg}} / \text{million years} \stackrel{?}{\approx} .007\% \text{ of } V_u / \text{million years}$$

Q_{seg} can be expressed in m^3 per million years, from EQ. 3 above. And, substitution of the numerical value for the volume of the universe V_u yields:

$$9.2 \times 10^{62} (3.15 \times 10^{13} \text{ s/million years}) \stackrel{?}{\approx} .00007 (4 \times 10^{80}) / \text{million years}$$

$$.00029 \times 10^{80} \text{ m}^3 / \text{million years} \approx .00028 \times 10^{80} \text{ m}^3 / \text{million years}$$

lending credibility to the concepts offered in this paper. See *Conclusions* for detailed discussion.

CONCLUSIONS

The conceptual model of the universe in Fig. 2 has proven surprisingly accurate and useful, considering that only the values for the age, the volume, and an assumed duration of the WFC for the universe were initially available.

The underlying premise that our present reality is only the most recently refreshed segment of many such segments comprising the universe is bolstered by the realistic magnitudes of the sample numerical calculations. Equations 1 through 5 are elementary yet useful and enlightening, as was the goal. No inconsistencies in the conceptual theory arose in calculations or in logic, including the criteria for a segment, i.e., nebulous interfaces and seamless transition to the previous or forthcoming segment.

Taken literally, the calculated value of segment height h_{seg} (Eq. 1) of approximately $.23 \times 10^{-19}$ m is several magnitudes shorter than even the shortest common subatomic wavelengths. This was by design, as discussed in *Assumption (g)*, and is not of concern, since the envisioned segments *seamlessly* enable uninterrupted overflow of intact wavelengths into the subsequently established segments of both space and time.

Likewise, the calculated approximate volume for the present segment V_{seg} (Eq. 2) of $.92 \times 10^{41}$ m³ denotes the region of space-time which would undergo refresh changes during the WFC, and seems large enough to encapsulate all that the quantum elements might have to deliver, especially considering its overwhelming surface area. Again the calculations are being taken literally, with license. Also, V_{seg} is reassuringly magnitudes less than the flow rate Q_{seg} (EQ. 3) which theoretically replenishes it.

Of particular interest is the calculated **velocity or progression of time in the present v_t** (Eq. 4). Without an apparent reference point, **the human observer might judge the calculated value of 230 m/s as either "slow" or "fast", however this would indicate a purely emotional response.** The modelled reference point is $t=0$ as shown in Fig. 2. Recall that this progression rate theoretically occurs over a distance of $.23 \times 10^{-19}$ m and a time of an assumed $.1 \times 10^{-21}$ s.

Generally, concerning Fig. 3 as already discussed, these flow rate Q_{seg} and velocity v_{seg} calculations are

admittedly one-dimensional solutions to multi-dimensional situations. A more accurately descriptive hybrid equation combining both would be

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{Multi-directional/multi-dimensional} \\ \text{progression of space through time} \\ \text{locally or globally} \end{array} = \frac{V_{\text{seg}} \text{ expressed in distances}}{V_{\text{seg}} \text{ expressed in times } \neq 1} \quad \frac{l \times w \times h \text{ meters}}{l \times w \times h \text{ seconds } \neq 1}$$

although no numerical value is available for either V_{seg} since the shapes of those supposedly locally distorted volumes are not known. Note that the denominator in this equation is not meant to be reduced to *per one second*, or a circularity again results wherein only a perfectly cubical time is being addressed.

Finally, **the verification of EQ. 5 in the sample calculations regarding expansion of the universe is very encouraging, and as mentioned, lends credibility to the concepts offered in this paper.** Based on the assumption that whatever enters the universe realm must either exit at some point, or be absorbed, inviting expansion, the calculated **influx flow rate Q_{seg} per million years almost exactly equals the current estimate for the expansion rate of the universe per million years.**

Of course, calculated results will change slightly with alternate assumptions, and with better input data over time, as our knowledge of the observable universe improves. This author invites such iterations by other researchers.

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